

Bibl.
85/1804r

Int. Rice Res. Newslett. 10(5):16
International Rice Research Institute
 P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines

Effect of some media components and organic additives on callus induction in rice anther culture

F.J. Zapata and L.B. Torrizo. Tissue Culture Facility, IRRRI

One constraint in rice anther culture is the low frequency of callus induction. Although we can trigger high frequency of callus induction in liquid medium, only a few anthers may respond. We sought to induce a high number of anthers that produce calli by determining the effect of some media components and organic additives — N, mannitol, coconut water, and mashed banana — on callus production.

Taipei 309 anthers at mid-uninucleate to early binucleate development were inoculated in Linbro multiwell plates. Individual anthers were placed in 1.0- × 0.6-cm wells at a plating density of 1 anther/0.3 ml medium. They were plated horizontally with the lower surface touching the medium. Cold treatment at 10 °C for 8 d followed. Then the plates were kept in darkness at 25 °C for 6 wk,

after which we recorded the number of anthers that produced calli. E₁₀ semisolid — a modification of Gamborg's B-5 medium — was used as the base medium in all four experiments.

In the N content experiment, the E₁₀ control had optimum concentration for inducing maximum anther-producing calli (see table). NH₄⁺ was added to E₁₀ medium as 134 mg (NH₄⁺)₂SO₄/litre and NO₃⁻ was added as 2500 mg KNO₃/litre.

Adding mannitol at 1% stimulated the most anthers and induced almost 1.5 times as many calli as the control. Although not considered as a readily available C source, mannitol may influence the medium's osmotic potential, a critical factor in callus induction.

Coconut water contains myo-inositol, growth regulators, and aminoacids, which can increase callus production.

Adding 10% coconut water produced 1.4 times the calli in the control. Mashed banana increases plantlet formation in immature orchid embryos, but inhibits rice callus induction. *S*

Effect of some media component and organic additives on callus induction in Taipei No. 309, IRRRI.

Treatment	Anthers plated (no.)	Anther-producing calli	
		no.	%
		<i>N^a</i>	
E ₁₀	149	21	14
E ₁₀ - 0.5 N	149	16	11
E ₁₀ - 1.5 N	149	17	11
E ₁₀ - 2.0 N	149	8	5
		<i>Mannitol^b</i>	
E ₁₀	168	30	18
E ₁₀ - M ₁	168	43	26
E ₁₀ - M ₂	168	35	21
E ₁₀ - M ₃	168	26	15
		<i>Coconut water^c</i>	
E ₁₀	185	18	10
E ₁₀ - C ₅	185	16	9
E ₁₀ - C ₁₀	185	25	13
E ₁₀ - C ₁₅	185	17	9
		<i>Mashed banana^d</i>	
E ₁₀	223	23	10
E ₁₀ - B ₅	223	23	10
E ₁₀ - B ₁₀	223	14	6
E ₁₀ - B ₁₅	223	2	1

^aN concentration (NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻) relative to E₁₀ in the control were 0.5, 1.5, and 2.0 times that of E₁₀. ^bMannitol concentrations were 0, 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0% wt/vol. ^cCoconut water concentrations were 0, 5.0, 10.0, and 15.0% vol/vol. ^dMashed banana concentrations were 0, 5, 10, and 15% wt/vol.